

Evaluation of Biogas Purification Potential of Clay, Potash, and Activated Coconut Shell Charcoal

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Abstract: Biogas purification is very vital in the production process of biogas. It involves the removal of impurities so as to improve the efficiency of methane. Although, reagents such as quicklime, Iron fillings, silica gel etc., can be used to purify biogas but the above reagents are expensive and not readily available to average Nigeria, thus this research work. This present work is focused on the evaluation of biogas purification potential of clay, potash, and activated coconut shell charcoal. A cylindrical filter made with transparent polyethylene outer casing was loaded with clay, potash, and activated coconut shells charcoal. A second filter which served as control set up was loaded with Silica gel, Iron fillings and quicklime. The results obtained were analyzed for percentage composition of biogas and the activeness of the purifying reagents used. The results showed an improvement in methane from 66.25% to 74.89% with coconut shells activated charcoal, 66.25% to 76.08% with potash, 66.25% to 73.88% with clay, and 66.25% to 82.37% when the reagents were used together. Therefore, the evaluated reagents can be used for the purification of biogas.

Keywords: Potash, Clay, Coconut shells, Biogas, Purification, Methane

INTRODUCTION

Biogas comprises of 50-70% methane (CH₄), 30-40% carbon dioxide (CO₂), and 5-10% of other gases such as hydrogen sulphide (H₂S), water vapour (H₂O) (Ray *et al.*, 2013, Franco *et al.*, 2015, Orhorhoro *et al.*, 2018). Biogas is a non-toxic, colourless and flammable gas. It has an ignition temperature of 650°C-750°C, its density is 1.214kg/ m³ (assuming about 60% CH₄ and 40% CO₂). Its calorific value is 20 MJ/m³ (or 4700 kcal.); it is almost 20% lighter than air (Sreela-or *et al.*, 2011). Biogas, like Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) cannot be converted into liquid state under normal temperature and pressure as it liquefies at a pressure of about 47.4 Kg/cm² and at a critical temperature of -82.1°C (Simonya and Fasina, 2013). One aspect of biogas production from anaerobic digestion process that requires special attention in Nigeria is the technology for the removal of impurities associated with the production of biogas (Orhorhoro *et al.*, 2018). Little is known about the effort to develop a local technology for the purification and removal of dangerous impurities before biogas can be used. Biogas purification is the process of removing unwanted by-products such as CO₂ that is incombustible, H₂S, H₂O, and other by-products present in it (Ebunilo *et al.*, 2016). Removing CO₂, H₂S, H₂O and compressing it into cylinders makes it easily usable for transport applications and also for stationary applications. Purified biogas (bio-methane) has a high calorific value in comparison to raw biogas (Ebunilo *et al.*, 2015). Already biogas technology has become

easily available and therefore, bio-methane (purified biogas) which is nearly same as LNG, can be used for all applications for which LNG are used.

Methane (CH₄) also known as marsh gas is a powerful greenhouse gas if emitted into the atmosphere, but can also represent a valuable renewable energy source, with the potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions when it is collected and substituted for fossil fuels. Biogas can be used directly to generate power, cook, etc., but the large volume of CO₂ produced with it reduces the heating value of the gas, increases compression and transportation costs and limits economic usability (Kim *et al.*, 2004). However, purification allows for a wider variety of uses, either for heat and electricity, or for vehicle fuels. For use as a fuel, purification to remove CO₂ and H₂S is required, because H₂S corrodes vital mechanical components within engine generator sets and vehicle if it is not removed (Yuan and Bandosz, 2007). On the other hand, removing CO₂ increases the heating value and leads to a consistent gas quality, similar to natural gas (Appels *et al.*, 2008). Although, H₂S is present in small quantity in biogas, the presence of H₂S usually prohibits the direct use of these gases because of its toxic properties, the formation of sulphur (IV) oxide (SO₂) upon combustion (acid rain), and the problems it (usually) gives in downstream processing (Osunde *et al.*, 2017). Beside, H₂S is frequently encountered in the field of odour monitoring because of its high odoriferous power (Zaouak *et al.*, 2012). On the other hand, purified biogas provides reductions in GHG emissions as well as several other environmental benefits when used as a cooking fuel, vehicle fuel, lightening fuel etc. Hence, there is need for proper purification of biogas.

In this research work, locally source materials such potash, coconut shells, and clay were evaluated mainly to investigate their biogas purification potential. Local potash is a brownish or blackish substance (due to impurities) but when pure, it is white in appearance. Its chemical configuration is potassium trioxocarbonate (IV) (K₂CO₃). It is deliquescent solid, thus a good drying agent (Deer *et al.*, 1992). Coconut shell is a bio-waste and it possesses the following properties such as low density, low cost, lower pollution, good thermal properties, and biodegradability over traditional reinforcing filler such as glass and carbon (Oksman, and Clemons, 1998). Dried coconut shell contains 33.61% cellulose, 36.51% lignin, 29.27% pentosans and 0.61% ash (Nagarajan *et al.*, 2014). It has low ash content but high volatile matter, 65-75% (Shelke *et al.*, 2014). The water absorption of the coconut shell is higher than usual aggregate, which is 24% compared to 0.5 (Gunasekaran *et al.*, 2012). Clay is a substance that is extensively distributed over the surface of the earth. It is found almost everywhere but differs greatly in its purity. Clay is a fine-grained natural rock or soil materials that combines one or more clay minerals with traces of metal oxides and organic matters (Ehlers and Blatt, 1982). Clay is plastics due to their water contents and become hard, brittle and non-plastic upon drying and frying (Guggenheim, 1995).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIALS

The materials used in this research work include; coconut shell (Fig. 1), potash (Fig. 2), clay (Fig. 3), biogas gas mild steel digester, weighing balanced, hand gloves, biogas compressor, storage cylinder, homemade scrubber with plastic, gas analyzer.

Fig.1 Coconut Shells

Fig.2 Local Potash

Fig.3 Clay

The usage of the materials are summarized in Table 1

Table 1 Materials and their Usage

S/N	Materials	Usage
1	Activated coconut shell ash	To react and remove H ₂ S
2	Calcium Oxide	To remove both Carbon dioxide and Water vapour
3	Iron sponge	Served as base support
4	Silica gel	To identify the presence of water
5	Iron fillings	To identify the presence of H ₂ S
6	Polyethene cylindrical container	To house both filters and controls
7	Oven	For drying the activated coconut shell charcoal
8	Burning sink	For burning the coconut shell
9	Calcium chloride	For activating the coconut shell charcoal
10	Draining tray	For removing moisture from the ash
11	Sterilized water	For washing
12	Digester	For generating biogas

METHODS

A. Preparation of Activated Coconut Shell Charcoal

Coconut shells collected from local market in Nigeria were collected and washed thoroughly with clean water and allowed to dry completely in a laboratory oven in order to facilitate its combustion. The coconut shells were burned completely to charcoal. 250g of Calcium Chloride (CaCl₂) was dissolved in 1000ml of water as chemical activator as recommended by Osunde *et al.*, 2018.

The dissolved CaCl₂ solution was poured into a beaker containing the coconut shell charcoal. The beaker was covered and left to cool for a period of 24 hours. The prepared CaCl₂ were impregnated into the coconut shell charcoal. The charcoal was removed from the CaCl₂ solution and transferred into a draining tray and it was allowed to drain for 24 hours. The charcoal was removed, washed in sterilized water repeatedly, and transferred to a laboratory oven with a temperature set at about 105°C to adequately dry it. The charcoal was removed from the oven after proper drying and crushed in a blender.

B. Preparation of the Filter

The activated coconut shell charcoal, clay and potash were impregnated on separate iron sponges and placed in the cylindrical polyethene container as recommended by Orhorhoro *et al.*, 2018 (Fig. 4). Each of the reagent purifier (i.e., potash, clay, and activated coconut shell charcoal) were used separately and used together. The reagents were arranged in this order; the sponge with clay was inserted first followed with that of the potash, and activated coconut shell charcoal. A separate filter with the following purifier reagents silica gel, quicklime and Iron fillings served as the control setup. Both filters were placed in series and the gas was passed through it to the storage cylinder. 0.5 kg of biogas was evacuated for gas analysis to know the percentage composition of the constituents of biogas present, and percentage composition of methane after purification.

Fig.4 Filter Arrangement

C. Chemistry of the Process

The chemistry of the process is shown in Equation (1)-Equation (6)

For Clay

For Potash

For Coconut Shell (CS)

D. Digester

The digester has a capacity of 0.15 m³ and is made with mild steel. It has an inlet valve for charging of formed slurry from co-digestion of organic fraction of domestic wastes collected from households in Warri, a thermometer for taking the temperature of the slurry, pressure gauge for taking the gas pressure, outlet valve for discharge of slurry, stirrer for continuous stirring of slurry, and gas discharging valve for evacuation of biogas are all connected to the digester. The method involves removal of non-biodegradable materials from the domestic waste. The organic fraction of domestic waste was reduced to smaller sizes by cutting it with knife. The wastes were mixed with water in a ratio of 1:2 as recommended by Ebunilo *et al.*, 2015. The slurry in the digester was continuously stirred and left for anaerobic digestion to take place. The pressure gauge was continuously monitored for the production of biogas and flame test was immediately carried out once the pressure gauge indicates an increase. Formation of blue flame is a confirmation of proper production of biogas. At this stage the biogas produced is evacuated for purification with local materials and control set up filter. A manual compressor was used to compress the biogas for analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the results of percentage composition of raw biogas while Table 3-Table 6 show the results of percentage composition of methane after purification with potash, clay, activated coconut shell charcoal used separately and when used together. The results obtained revealed that the percentage composition of raw biogas obtained from anaerobic co-digestion of organic domestic waste comprises of 66.25% of CH₄, 30.01% of CO₂, 2.45% of H₂O, and 1.29% of H₂S. These results obtained agreed with the research work of Ebunilo *et al.* (2016) that reported similar results in their research work. However, other major impurities were such as siloxane, ammonia was not present but this could be as a result of the composition of substrates used. According to Nwokode (2015), siloxane is only present in municipal solid waste due to the present of wastes from cosmetic that combined with organic waste. Also, research work of Ray *et al* (2013) shows that landfill biogas contains ammonia, and Nitrogen. However, in this scenario, the wastes were not from open dump site and landfill but collected from households. From Table 3, there was increased in the average percentage composition of methane from 66.25% to 85.75% with control setup and 76.08% with potash. The increase in the percentage composition of methane confirmed the removal of impurities from the raw biogas with the use of potash. The results obtained show that potash has the ability to purify biogas and this was responsible for the increase in the percentage composition of methane obtained after purification since more of impurities were removed. The result obtained with coconut shell charcoal is shown in Table 5. The improvement in the percentage composition of methane produced when compared to the quantity obtains after evacuation (raw biogas) implies that activated coconut shell charcoal has the ability to purify biogas. There was increased in the average percentage composition of methane from 66.25% to 86.50% with control setup and 74.89% with activated coconut shell charcoal.

Table2 Percentage (%) Composition of Raw Biogas

CH ₄	CO ₂	H ₂ O	H ₂ S
66.25%	30.01%	2.45%	1.29%

Table3 Comparative Analysis of Average Percentage (%) Composition of Methane after Purification with Potash

S/N	% Composition of CH ₄ after purification with Control Setup	% Composition of CH ₄ after Purification with Potash
	84.50	76.46
2	85.20	76.45
3	86.50	75.96
4	86.80	75.43
Σn=4	Σ=343.0	Σ=304.30
	A=85.75	A=76.08

Table4 Comparative Analysis of Average Percentage (%) Composition of Methane after Purification with Clay

S/N	% Composition of CH ₄ after purification with Control Setup	% Composition of CH ₄ after Purification with Clay
1	88.70	73.89
2	88.71	73.55
3	88.69	74.05
4	88.73	74.01
Σn=4	Σ=354.83	Σ=295.50
	A=88.71	A=73.88

Table5 Comparative Analysis of Average Percentage (%) Composition of Methane after Purification with Activated Coconut Shells Charcoal

S/N	% Composition of CH ₄ after purification with Control Setup	% Composition of CH ₄ after Purification with Activated Coconut Shells Charcoal
1	85.20	74.67
2	86.85	75.23
3	86.90	74.82
4	87.05	74.79
Σn=4	Σ=346.0	Σ=299.51
	A=86.50	A=74.89

Also, the three reagents purifiers were used together. Table 6 showed the results obtained when the reagents purifier were used together. The average percentage composition of methane with the reagents used together and control set up reagents were calculated as 82.37% and 88.46% and this simply showed that using the reagents together is more efficiency than using it separately. Besides, the percentage composition of methane obtained were close, thus clay, potash and activated coconut shell charcoal can be used in the placed of know purifier such as silica gel, quick lime and Iron fillings.

Table6 Comparative Analysis of Average Percentage (%) Composition of Methane after Purification with Combination of Clay, Potash, and Activated Coconut Shell Charcoal

S/N	% Composition of CH ₄ after purification with Control Setup	% Composition of CH ₄ after Purification with Clay, Potash, and Activated Coconut Shell Charcoal
1	88.05	82.42
2	87.85	81.90
3	88.98	82.20
4	88.94	82.95
Σn=4	Σ=353.82	Σ=329.47
	A=88.46	A=82.37

CONCLUSION

In this research work, a new reagent that can be used to purify biogas was evaluated for performance. The results obtained show that clay, activated coconut shell charcoal, and potash have the ability of removing impurities such CO₂, H₂S from raw biogas. The percentage composition analysis of biogas before and after purification with clay shows an improvement of methane from 66.25% to 73.88% with potash, 66.25% to 76.08% with activated coconut shells charcoal, 66.25% to 74.89% when used, 66.25% to 82.37%. Therefore, raw biogas can be purified using clay, potash and activated coconut shells charcoal.

RECOMMENDATION

Further studies should be carried out to investigate modal analysis of wind turbine tower using different geometries of the wind turbine tower. This will help ascertain best geometries of wind turbine tower.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest associated with this work.

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